

Iban

also known as “Sea Dayaks”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Religion, Southeast Asian Religions

The Iban are a group of people who inhabit the island of Borneo, but the largest numbers of Iban are found in the Malaysian state of Sarawak. The Iban live in family longhouses known as bileks; each bilek is autonomous, and is the primary social and economic unit. Religious beliefs and practices permeate all aspects of Iban life, including social organization, agricultural practices, and customary law (Jensen, 1974:5). For this reason, this entry considers the Iban religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. The Iban believe in a variety of supernatural beings including deities, demon-like spirits, spirits of dead and living humans, and many nature spirits. Rice is an anthropomorphized supernatural being, and plays a significant role in agricultural ceremonies. In addition to agricultural ceremonies, other types of rituals include healing rituals, ceremonies for the courageous, and rituals for the deceased (Sutlive and Beierle, 1995). Religious specialists include the tuai burong (augur), tuai rumah (village headman), lemambang (bard), and manang (shaman). This entry focuses on the Malaysian state of Sarawak around the time of 1950.

Date Range: 1941 CE - 1966 CE

Region: Sarawak, Borneo Island

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Malaysia

Sarawak, Malaysian state on Borneo Island circa 1950

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). Ethnographic Atlas. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oc06-021>
- Source 1 Description: Jensen, E. (1974). *Iban And Their Religion*. Oxford Monographs On Social Anthropology. Oxford, Eng.: Oxford University Press.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oc06-000>
- Source 2 Description: Sutlive Jr, V. H., & Beierle, J. (1995). *Culture Summary: Iban*. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.
- Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oc06-015>
- Source 3 Description: Freeman, D. (1955). *Report On The Iban Of Sarawak: Vol. 1: Iban Social Organization*. Kuching, Sarawak: Government Printing Office.
- Notes: Source 3 is referred to as Freeman, 1955b in this entry.
- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oc06-019>
- Source 1 Description: Freeman, D. (1981). *Some Reflections On The Nature Of Iban Society*. Occasional Paper Of The Department Of Anthropology, Research School Of Pacific Studies, The Australian National University. Canberra, A.C.T.: Dept. of Anthropology, Research School of Pacific Studies, Australian National University.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oc06-022>
- Source 2 Description: Graham, P. (1987). *Iban Shamanism: An Analysis Of The Ethnographic Literature*. Occasional Paper Of The Department Of Anthropology, Research School Of Pacific Studies, The Australian National University. Canberra, A.C.T.: [Department of Anthropology, Research School of Pacific Studies, the Australian National University].

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Hinduism has touched the Iban, as the title for a deity (Petara) and the names of some of the spirits imply. But neither Hinduism nor Islam has radically influenced Iban religion which remains a cult based on a belief in the spirits of men, nature, and super-nature" (Jensen, 1974:4).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Iban were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Iban were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: "The Iban are not concerned to convert others to their view of life" (Jensen, 1974:213).

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "The Iban themselves express the connection and interdependence of their social organization, agricultural practice, and religion most succinctly when they say: adat kami bumai. This means 'we farm (hill rice) and live according to the order revealed by the spirits.' The word adat, which is normally translated 'customary law', may mean much more than this. To the Iban it involves the basic values of life, their system of agriculture, as well as the code according to which their society is ordered. It also concerns the 'correct' manner of behaviour. Adat is applied not only to men but also to animals and to natural phenomena" (Jensen, 1974:5).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 237741

Notes: See: Jensen, 1974:14 (population figures for 1960)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 32

Notes: See: Jensen, 1974:14 (population figures for 1960)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The personnel of Iban religion, the experts, are those individuals who have specific roles in relation to rice cultivation, augury, ritual celebrations and the ordering of society. They act as a channel between the world of immediate experience and its spirit antecedents and influences. The leading exponents of these roles in Iban society are four, although one or more functions may be vested in the same person. They are the tuai burong or augur, the tuai rumah or village headman, the lemambang or ritual incantation specialist, and, lastly, the manang--shaman or 'healer'" (Jensen, 1974:59).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "Knowledge of Iban mythology and their conception of the spirit world is contained in a rich oral tradition. There are a number of recognized (literary) forms: pengap, sampi, pelian, tusut, kana, renong, pantun, jerita tuai, ensera" (Jensen, 1974:64).

↳ Are they written:

– No

Notes: (Jensen, 1974:64)

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: "Knowledge of Iban mythology and their conception of the spirit world is contained in a rich oral tradition. There are a number of recognized (literary) forms: pengap, sampi, pelian, tusut, kana, renong, pantun, jerita tuai, ensera" (Jensen, 1974:64).

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: "The main myths all concern the spirit ancestry of the Iban and the origins of their religious beliefs, ritual, and social code. Although these are remarkably consistent, some variants and even contradictions occur...The Iban see no need to resolve the inconsistencies...Nor do they appeal to the authority of papan turai or any one person" (Jensen, 1974:71-72).

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: "It is correct that certain individuals have a reputation for knowing the mythology and these are frequently asked to recount the myths in whole or in part, but no single individual has broad authority" (Jensen, 1974:72).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972), column 6 Large or Impressive Structures [Note: Identical to SCCS Variable 66], "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972), column 6 Large or Impressive Structures [Note: Identical to SCCS Variable 66], "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "When an Iban dies he is said 'to become an (antu) spirit' (nyadi antu). His life-giving spirit/soul abandons the body but continues to have a spirit existence. Although the spirits of dead men have their own menoa , Sebayan, the spirit of the man who has recently died does not immediately settle down in Sebayan. Until the final burial rites have been performed, the spirit is thought to be without an established territory and is likely to come searching for food and firewood; consequently surviving relatives leave offerings and gifts in and around the longhouse to placate the spirit of the dead which might turn aggressive if thwarted, frustrated, or left hungry. The samengat remains as an antu spirit in Sebayan for an indefinite period until eventually dissolving into dew. The dew is taken up into the ears of rice which are eaten by living men who in their turn die" (Jensen, 1974:108).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "In dreams, the samengat [soul/spirit] of man has experiences which are independent of the sleeping body. While the body remains asleep in one place, the samengat may wander abroad and in doing so it frequently encounters non-human spirits. In dreams, the samengat which has the properties of a spirit moves in the spirit world" (Jensen, 1974:116).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The position is perhaps best illustrated by considering Iban death customs. The Iban have an absolute and fervent belief in the immortality of the soul, and in the existence of an After-World, which they call Sabayan. To this shadowy land go the souls of all the Iban dead--men, women and children" (Freeman, 1955b:14).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: "But Sebayan, land of the dead, lies below the earth. It is approached by river from a specific geographical point, the Mandai river, which is situated in the upper reaches of the Kapuas (beyond the point where the Iban originally entered Sarawak). The inverted bowl analogy helps to explain the apparent opposites which characterize Sebayan. Night, for example, for the living on earth, is day in Sebayan; consequently the spirits of the dead are most commonly encountered in dreams, at night, when Sebayan is awake and abroad" (Jensen, 1974:104).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Bodies of the deceased are interred (See Freeman, 1955b:14).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Bodies of the deceased are interred (See Freeman, 1955b:14).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, indicates that secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Sabayan indeed, is looked upon as being an almost exact replica of this world, and it therefore becomes the solemn duty of the living to equip the dead for their future existence. This is done by providing every dead person with burial property, or baiya...These objects are either buried with the corpse...or left lying on the surface of the grave; and it is believed that all these objects--in their shape as soul-stuff--are taken to the After-World by the soul of the dead man" (Freeman, 1955b:14).

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "This burial property includes an exceedingly wide range of articles, from clothing, padi seed, cooking utensils, tools, ornaments and weapons, to precious jars, gongs and fabrics" (Freeman, 1955b:14).

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: (Freeman, 1955b:14)

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: (Freeman, 1955b:14)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The providing of a man's burial property and the performing of the accompanying funerary rites is a costly business, but it is a duty which is always faithfully carried out" (Freeman, 1955b:15).

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "Nor, among the Iban, is there anything resembling a village green (such as the marae of Polynesia), which belongs to the community as a whole. Privately owned land approaches to within a few feet of the long-house structure. The only exception is the burial ground, or pendam. This invariably consists of a spur rising from the river, on the banks of which the long-house is situated, for corpses are always carried by canoe. The jungle on the chosen spur is left in its primeval state, and never entered except for burials and on ritual occasions. Here, all bilek-families inter their dead, and throughout the undergrowth (for graves are left untended) are scattered jars, gongs, and many other kinds of burial property, which constitute the last inheritance of the dead" (Freeman, 1955b:45).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family tomb-crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of domestic burials.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The universe is inhabited by two types of divine or demon-like spirits: petara and antu , the spirits of dead men (antu) as well as of the living, animal and vegetable: men (mensia), mammals and other animals (jelu), reptiles, i.e. snakes (ular) etc., birds (burong), fish (ikan), insects (indu utai), trees (kayu), and plant-life--leaves and grasses (daun, rumput)" (Jensen, 1974:100).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], indicates that a high god is absent among the Iban (Murdock, 1962-1971;

Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "When an Iban dies he is said 'to become an (antu) spirit' (nyadi antu). His life-giving spirit/soul abandons the body but continues to have a spirit existence. Although the spirits of dead men have their own menoa , Sebayan, the spirit of the man who has recently died does not immediately settle down in Sebayan. Until the final burial rites have been performed, the spirit is thought to be without an established territory and is likely to come searching for food and firewood; consequently surviving relatives leave offerings and gifts in and around the longhouse to placate the spirit of the dead which might turn aggressive if thwarted, frustrated, or left hungry" (Jensen, 1974:108).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "When an Iban dies he is said 'to become an (antu) spirit' (nyadi antu). His life-giving spirit/soul abandons the body but continues to have a spirit existence. Although the spirits of dead men have their own menoa , Sebayan, the spirit of the man who has recently died does not immediately settle down in Sebayan. Until the final burial rites have been performed, the spirit is thought to be without an established territory and is likely to come searching for food and firewood; consequently surviving relatives leave offerings and gifts in and around the longhouse to placate the spirit of the dead which might turn aggressive if thwarted, frustrated, or left hungry" (Jensen, 1974:108).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "None matters more than the personified spirit/soul of rice, samengat padi , to which human emotions and responses are regularly attributed and with which the samengat [soul] of man is ultimately identified" (Jensen, 1974:109).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Most of the spirits are anthropomorphically conceived. In 'person' they resemble human beings and they have human ways of thinking and emotions. Like men, they may experience jealousy, resentment, fear, and even hatred, but their positive feelings are uppermost. Like men they are also liable to caprice. But because they have human feelings and responses, the Iban is not only capable of understanding the spirits but also of entering into a meaningful relationship with them, not unlike the relations he establishes with his fellow men" (Jensen, 1974:210).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Most of the spirits are anthropomorphically conceived. In 'person' they resemble human beings and they have human ways of thinking and emotions. Like

men, they may experience jealousy, resentment, fear, and even hatred, but their positive feelings are uppermost. Like men they are also liable to caprice. But because they have human feelings and responses, the Iban is not only capable of understanding the spirits but also of entering into a meaningful relationship with them, not unlike the relations he establishes with his fellow men" (Jensen, 1974:210).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The universe is inhabited by two types of divine or demon-like spirits: petara and antu , the spirits of dead men (antu) as well as of the living, animal and vegetable: men (mensia), mammals and other animals (jelu), reptiles, i.e. snakes (ular) etc., birds (burong), fish (ikan), insects (indu utai), trees (kayu), and plant-life--leaves and grasses (daun, rumput)" (Jensen, 1974:100).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: "Iban genealogies (tusut) preserve the record of their ancestry from the spirit world. The average number of generations remembered is slightly over twenty from Sengalang Burong to the present day...The tables are learned by rote; because of the use of internal rhyme and the poetic form, a block of several names is more easily omitted than an isolated individual" (Jensen, 1974:95).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "Like men-spirit relations social behaviour among men is closely regulated, and serious offences, such as incest, are believed to disturb the total order. Even minor offences, if left unresolved, are liable to have consequences not only for the individual and bilek concerned, but for the health and prosperity of the community as a whole. Poor harvests, barren soil, sickness, and early death, since they have spirit origins, are attributed to disturbances causing an imbalance in the universal order of behaviour; they should not occur but for a breach of adat. While the routine rites and ritual take into account the possibility of unheeded transgressions, special ceremonies make provision for ritual action consciously designed to heal known breaches of adat" (Jensen, 1974:212).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: "As already mentioned (see above, p. 40), incest provides the most important example, murder another" (Jensen, 1974:113).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: (Jensen, 1974:212)

Incest:

– Yes

Notes: "Like men-spirit relations social behaviour among men is closely regulated, and serious offences, such as incest, are believed to disturb the total order" (Jensen, 1974:212).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: "An offence against adat disturbs the universal order, producing disorder and the undesirable 'heated' or 'feverish' state, *angat*. The results of disorder range from minor sickness to epidemics and crop failure. Lesser transgressions may affect only the bilek concerned, although this is not necessarily so since an offence against adat disrupts the total order. The consequences are more the result of this disturbance than punishment inflicted on the guilty. Serious transgression of adat invariably touches the whole community" (Jensen, 1974:113).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Adat [customary law] governs both the Iban and the spirits; it expresses the 'true' ordered behaviour of all facets of the universe, animal, vegetable, human, and spirit, and it lays down the ideal behaviour patterns and relationships, rights, and responsibilities. When the Iban say *adat kami bumai* they summarize the essence and function of the code as it affects them: 'we farm (hill rice) and live according to the order made known by the spirits.' The rules and the ritual, designed to ensure adequate harvests, are central to the prosperity of the Iban whose fortunes, socially and individually, are governed by *adat*" (Jensen, 1974:211).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the requirement of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Minor celebrations and smaller rituals are held when necessary. "The first [category of gawai rituals] are incidental celebrations, which are generally confined to one or two families and are not significant in the wider context. These may be occasioned by sickness, recovery from sickness, fear of sickness (for example, cholera, when the rumour of an epidemic is current), a dream, an omen, setting off on an expedition (bejalai), enlisting in the police or armed forces, returning from military service, or simply because someone 'feels like a party' (rindu) and offers an appropriate pretext" (Jensen, 1974:195).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "Iban rituals (Gawa, Gawai) may be grouped into four major categories: (1) one dozen major and three dozen minor ones agricultural festivals; (2) healing rituals, performed by the shaman, commencing in the Bilek and progressing to the outer veranda; (3) ceremonies for the courageous, commemorating warfare and headhunting; and (4) rituals for the dead. Iban of all divisions perform

rituals of the first two categories. Ceremonies to honor warriors has assumed greater importance in the upper Rejang, and rituals for the dead have been much more elaborated in the First and Second Divisions of Sarawak" (Sutlive and Beierle, 1995).

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are led by various religious specialists including the tuai burong (augur, involved with daily activities of religion), the tuai rumah or village headman, lemamband or ritual incantation specialist, or the manang or shaman.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Iban have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However the longhouse community structure of the Iban extended beyond the local group, which is reflective of a tribe society (see Graham, 1987:8). Additionally, Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Iban have bilateral descent. Further, the Iban live in agamous communities without matrilineal or patrilineal kin groups/exogamy. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22. Although the Iban do not appear to have political organization beyond the community, a transition in political organization and establishment of a district-level political office occurred with the arrival of British influence (See Freeman, 1981:15-19).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education among the Iban.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education among the Iban.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Iban have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used among the Iban (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 9, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 89, Judiciary) indicates that "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community."

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Because the Iban do not have an institutionalized police force or judiciary, it can be assumed that institutionalized punishment is not present.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The Iban follow the adat order, which is best described as customary law (as opposed to a formal religious law). For more information on adat, see Jensen, 1974 pp. 111-116.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Iban rely primarily on extensive/shifting agriculture for subsistence. Fishing and pastoralism provide secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Iban rely primarily on extensive/shifting agriculture for subsistence. Fishing and pastoralism provide secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.